

Potentiometric Determination of Protonation Constants of some *o,o'*-Dihydroxy Schiff Bases and Stability Constants of their Nickel(II) Complexes

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It is well known that substituted salicylidene-2-hydroxyanilines are an important series of ligands with ONO donor system. There are two major factors influencing the basicities of the donor atoms in a ligand molecule, structural and solvent effects. Structural substituent effects on the basicities of *N*-salicylidene-2-hydroxyanilines in non-aqueous medium have been reported in our previous work¹. In the present work, protonation constants of ten substituted salicylidene-2-hydroxyanilines and their ML and ML₂ type complexes with Ni^{II} ion have been determined potentiometrically using FORTRAN program PKAS and BEST respectively. Substituent effects on these constants are discussed.

x	x'	Ligand
H	H	1
CH ₃	H	2
H	CH ₃	3
CH ₃	CH ₃	4
Cl	H	5
H	Cl	6
Cl	Cl	7
NO ₂	H	8
H	NO ₂	9
NO ₂	NO ₂	10

Results and Discussion

Protonation constants of the Schiff bases : Constants of the complexes are given in Table 1. All ligands have three protonation constants as expected. First and second constants K_1^H and K_2^H , refer to protonation of phenolate anions (1) and (2), and the third constant K_3^H refers to protonation of iminonitrogen atom (3) :

Table 1 shows that all three protonation constants of methyl substituted Schiff bases (2-4) are higher than that of unsubstituted Schiff base (1). In contrast, nitro substituted Schiff bases (8-10) have lower protonation constants than that of unsubstituted one. Because of electron-donating effect of methyl group, electron density of benzene ring(s) in 2-4 is higher than that of 1. Thus the basicities of phenolic oxygens increase. On the other hand, electron-withdrawing effect of nitro group decreases the electron density of the benzene ring(s) in 8-10 relative to compound 1. Hence the basicities of nitro substituted compounds are weaker than that of compound 1.

Table 1 also shows that the first and second protonation constants of chlorine substituted Schiff bases are higher but third constants are lower than those of unsubstituted ligand. This fact can be explained by dual character of chlorine. Higher values of $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ for 5-7 than those of 1 may be attributed to increasing electron density of oxygen atom(s) of hydroxy group(s) with resonance effect of chlorine atom. Contrarily, lower K_3^H values may be attributed to decreasing electron density of nitrogen atom of the imino group because of inductive electron-withdrawing effect of the chlorine atom(s).

Stability constants of the complexes : First, complex forming reactions of Schiff bases with Ni^{II} ion were investigated. For this purpose 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios of nick-

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves for Schiff base 1. 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 stoichiometries of Ni^{II}-to-Schiff base 1 as a function of added KOH, mol of base added/mol of metal ion (or ligand) present.

TABLE 1—PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES

Temp. = 25 ± 0.1°, μ = 0.1 M KCl

Substituent		Protonation constant		Stability constant		Substituent		Protonation constants		Stability constants	
x	x'	log K ₁ ^H	σ	log K ₁	σ _{fit}	x	x'	log K ₁ ^H	σ	log K ₁	σ _{fit}
H	H	10.4	0.01	12.52		H	Cl	10.59	0.01	12.09	
		9.19	0.01	6.60				9.17	0.01	6.26	
		4.13	0.06	19.12	0.01			3.69	0.08	18.35	0.02
CH ₃	H	10.81	0.01	11.74		Cl	Cl	10.67	0.01	11.36	
		9.71	0.02	6.02				9.09	0.02	5.94	
		4.21	0.07	17.76	0.03			3.32	0.07	17.30	0.03
		10.75	0.005	11.97		H	NO ₂	8.44	0.007	13.53	
H	CH ₃	9.47	0.01	6.15				7.69	0.01	6.82	
		4.26	0.04	18.12	0.01			3.35	0.05	20.35	0.03
		11.03	0.009	11.11		NO ₂	H	8.41	0.01	13.07	
CH ₃	CH ₃	9.82	0.01	5.70				7.74	0.01	6.58	
		4.40	0.05	16.81	0.03			3.14	0.06	19.65	0.03
		10.70	0.004	11.88		NO ₂	NO ₂	8.15	0.005	16.51	
Cl	H	9.14	0.01	6.13				7.49	0.01	7.36	
		3.83	0.06	18.01	0.02			2.81	0.05	23.87	0.02

el(II) ion with *N*-salicylidene-2-hydroxyaniline were titrated (Fig. 1). A break near *m* = 3 for ML system and near *m* = 6 for ML₂ system can be explained by the release of three protons for ML system and six protons for ML₂ system when the complexes were formed. Thus the complex formation equilibria are represented as follows :

As it is seen in Table 1, nitro substituted complexes have higher stability constants but methyl and chlorine substituted complexes have lower stability constants than those of the unsubstituted complex. This fact can be explained as follows. Two phenolic oxygen atoms of the ligand molecules besides forming σ-bonds with the metal ion, participate in π-interaction (dπ-pπ). Because of filled 2*p* orbitals, oxygen acts as a π-donor and can not accept electron density from the metal ion. Electron-withdrawing nitro group attached to the benzene ring in the ligand molecule decreases electron density of 2*p* orbitals of phenolic oxygen atom and π-interaction (M → L) increases to some extent. Thus stability of methyl and chlorine substituted complexes decreases. Similar results were observed for the ligand field stabilisation energies (10D_q values) of these complexes².

Experimental

All Schiff bases were synthesised³ by condensing appropriate amines and aldehydes in 1 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol.

A 50% (v/v) ethanol-water system prepared from triple-distilled water and absolute ethanol was used as a solvent. Ni^{II} solution was prepared from nickel chloride (Merck,

G.R.) and was standardised with EDTA titration⁴. Carbonate-free KOH (Merck) solution was standardised with potassium hydrogen phthalate. KCl and concentrated HCl (both Merck, extra pure) were used.

Potentiometric measurement : A Corning M-240 pH meter adopted to a Corning semimicro combination glass electrode (476050) was used. The electrode system was calibrated in terms of hydrogen ion concentration from strong acid-strong base titrations by the Gran method⁵. Titrations were performed using 25 ± 0.01 cm³ samples in the pH range 2–12 for Schiff bases and 3–9 for complexes in μ = 0.10 M KCl. Sample solutions were titrated in a double-walled glass cell maintained at 25 ± 0.1° and stirred under a continuous flow of N₂. The concentrations of the Schiff bases were about 2.5 × 10⁻³ M and metal-to-ligand mole ratio was 1 : 4. pH-meter readings in aquo-organic system were corrected⁶.

Protonation constants of the Schiff bases and stability constants of the complexes were calculated from potentiometric data using the FORTRAN program PKAS and BEST respectively⁷. The number of experimental points (v. pH) were between 46 and 64 for each titration. In refining the overall stability constants of the complexes with the program BEST, some experimental points around the equivalence point were neglected.

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